

Precipitation variation trends under the background of the climate variability

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Abstract

Climate variability has become a pressing issue in recent decades, with far-reaching impacts on various aspects of life. The consequences of climate variability are a major theme of humanity in the 21st century, and its effects on the global water cycle have been significant. In addition, human activities have contributed to an increase in extreme weather events as a part of climate variability, which are a direct consequence of climate variability.

This study aims to investigate the precipitation trends across Nghe An Province of Viet Nam under the background of climate variability. The study applies non-parametric statistical approaches including the Man-Kendall test and Sen's slope estimator to detect changes in precipitation based on the daily precipitation data series at four observation stations across Nghe An Province during the period of 1998-2022.

The results indicate that all four stations exhibit a trend towards increasing precipitation, with Dua station experiencing the strongest trend. The results also suggest that the rate of change in precipitation varies across the stations, with Yen Thuong and Nam Dan stations experiencing a moderate rate of change, while Do Luong station experiences a slight rate of increasing. These findings have important implications for water resource management and agricultural planning in the region.

Keywords: Climate variation, soil loss, famers, annual rainfall, Mann–Kendall test.

1. Introduction

In recent decades, climate variability has become a pressing issue in recent years, with far-reaching impacts on various aspects of life [1, 3]. The consequences of climate variability are a major theme of humanity in the 21st century [2, 18], and its effects on the global water cycle have been significant [4, 5]. In addition, human activities have led to an increase in extreme weather events as a part of climate variability, which are a direct consequence of climate variability [9, 13]. These events pose a substantial risk to agricultural productivity and soil health, particularly in areas prone to heavy rainfall [6, 10, 14]. Research has shown that the frequency of heavy rainfall events is increasing, which is a part of the larger trend of climate variability [7, 16]. Rainfall is a critical climatic factor that has a significant impact on various aspects of social life, particularly in agricultural cultivation areas [8, 9]. Changes in rainfall patterns can lead to a range of consequences, including yield loss, landslides, and soil erosion [11, 12, 15]. In high mountainous regions, these changes can result in income decline and soil loss [12, 17].

Globally, numerous studies have been conducted on the impact of climate variability on rainfall trends [1, 2]. These studies have employed various statistical approaches, including non-parametric and parametric methods, to detect changes in rainfall patterns and trends [9, 19]. Issued studies on the precipitation trends have been deployed in around the world, such as a trend analysis of rainfall the Aseer Region of Saudi Arabia by Al-Subih et al. (2021), a trend in precipitation days in the United States by Bartels et al. (2020), a change trend detection of future temperature and rainfall in the West Africa by Ilori et al. (2020); an analysis the change trends in precipitation in the sub-Himalayan region of Pakistan by Iqbal et al. (2019); a detect trends and changes in rainfall, temperature and wind speed in Burundi by Lawin et al. (2018).

This study aims to investigate the rainfall features trends across Nghe An Province of Viet Nam under the background of climate variability. The study will apply non-parametric statistical approaches to detect changes in rainfall patterns and trends. By understanding the trends in rainfall features, we hope to provide valuable insights into the potential risks associated with climate variability and inform policymakers and stakeholders on effective strategies to mitigate these risks.

2. Methods and materials

2.1 Study area

The study area is located in the North Central region of Vietnam, it is a vast and ecologically diverse region, covering an area of approximately 16,400 square kilometers (Figure 1). Characterized by its unique geography and climate, the province is a significant hub for agricultural and forestry activities [21]. With a population of approximately 3,419,989 people, the province's terrain is marked by a diverse range of topographic conditions, featuring mountains, hills, and plains with elevations ranging from 10 to over 1000 m a.m.s.l (Figure 1). The province's topography is characterized by a gentle slope from north to south and from west to east, with four distinct seasons: spring, summer, autumn, and winter [22].

Figure 1: Topographic map of the study area

The average annual temperature is around 23-24°C, with significant temperature fluctuations throughout the year [21, 22]. Nghe An receives an average annual rainfall up to 2,000 mm, with the majority of rainfall concentrated in the late summer and early autumn months, specifically August, September, and October (Figure 2). Notably, the rainfall distribution varies significantly across different areas of the province [22].

Figure 2: Monthly rainfall distribution at observation stations across Nghe An province

2.2 Data collection

To conduct this work, daily rainfall data at 04 observation stations across Nghe An province (Figure 2) were collected from the Hydrometeorological Forecasting Station in Nghe An province, Vietnam during the period 1998-2022. Accordingly, rainfall data series quality was appraised to ensure that the input rainfall data series meets the criteria for trend analysis.

2.3 Statistical approaches

2.3.1 Interruption point detection

To avoid interruption of observed rainfall data series, the study applied the Buishand test is a statistical technique used to detect cumulative deviations from the mean for evaluating the homogeneity of a time series [9, 23]. The Buishand test is based on characteristic statistical values such as the mean, variance, and standard deviation [23]. The Buishand test is expressed as:

$$S_0^* = 0; \quad S_k^* = \sum_{i=1}^k (Y_i - \bar{Y}), k = 1, \dots, n \quad (1)$$

where $S_0^* = 0$ is the value at point $k = 0$, which oscillates around 0 in the case where the time series is considered homogeneous, S_k^* is the value at point k , Y_i is the value at time i , and \bar{Y} is the mean of the series.

When evaluating the quality of the time series, two hypotheses are formulated in this problem:

1. H_0 (Null hypothesis): The time series exhibits homogeneity.
2. H_1 (Alternative hypothesis): The time series is non-homogeneous, with discontinuities at one or multiple points in the time series.

The confidence level of 95%, corresponding to a significance level of ($\alpha = 0.05$). If the p-value is greater than the significance level α , the null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted, and the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is rejected, indicating that the time series is homogeneous. Conversely, if the p-value is less than α , the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is accepted, signifying that the time series is non-homogeneous.

2.3.2 Change trend detection

To employ this work, a non-parametric statistical method, specifically the Mann-Kendall test and Sen's slope estimator, are applied to detect change trends of the rainfall data series during the period of 1998-2020. This method is predicated on the assumption of an H_0 of no trend, whereas a monotonic trend (i.e., an increasing or decreasing pattern) is posited as the alternative hypothesis (H_1) [9, 23]. The Mann-Kendall test is defined based on formula (2):

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=i+1}^n \text{sgn}(X_j - X_i) \quad (2)$$

Where $\text{sgn}(X_j - X_i)$ in formula (2) is defined by formula (3):

$$\text{sgn}(X_j - X_i) = \begin{cases} +1 & \text{if } x_j - x_i > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } x_j - x_i = 0 \\ -1 & \text{if } x_j - x_i < 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

In a time series, X_i , $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$, the value of S is assumed to be a normal distribution while the discrepancy of statistics S has signed applying formula (4):

$$\text{var}(S) = \frac{1}{18} [n(n-1)(2n+5) - \sum_{j=1}^m t_j(t_j-1)(2t_j+5)] \quad (4)$$

where the standard test (Z_s) is used to detect the input series trend. When the Z_s is calculated using formula (5):

$$Z_s = \begin{cases} \frac{S-1}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(S)}} & \text{if } S > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } S = 0 \\ \frac{S+1}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(S)}} & \text{if } S < 0 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

The Sen's slope estimator is also a non-parametric statistical method frequently employed to establish the true gradient of an existing trend [23]. Furthermore, it is often utilized to quantify the magnitude of change in trends observed in the data series [9]. The Sen's slope is computed using the following formula:

$$\beta = \text{Median} \left(\frac{X_i - X_j}{i - j} \right) \quad \text{with } j < i \quad (6)$$

where X_i , X_j are input series at intervals t_i and t_j , respectively.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Breakpoint detection

The daily rainfall data series at 4 observation stations across Nghe An province during the period 1998-2020 was transformed to annual rainfall before conducting the breakpoint detection applying test SNHT Buishand test. The results indicated that the obtained critical values (p) of 4 rainfall observation stations are larger than the confidence level 95% which implies that the input data series at all observation stations across the study area are of good quality and completely meets the requirements for further studies (Table 1 and Figure 1).

Table 1. Breakpoint detection for rainfall series at stations across Nghe An province

No.	Station	SNHT		Buishand	
		T _o	p	Q	p
1	Yen Thuong	2.787	0.590	3.786	0.445
2	Dua	3.918	0.317	4.117	0.358
3	Do Luong	5.042	0.188	4.563	0.237
4	Nam Dan	2.671	0.629	3.542	0.524

Figure 3: Quality assessment results of input data series at stations across the study area

3.2 Precipitation statistical features

Basic statistical features of the precipitation characteristics at 4 observation stations including Yen Thuong, Dua, Do Luong and Nam Dan across Nghe An province during the period 1998-2020 were given in Table 2. The minimum precipitation values at the four stations range from 1086.1 mm (Nam Dan station) to 1149.5 mm (Do Luong station), indicating that the driest period occurred in the east and northeast of the study area, with a minimum value of 1086.1 mm. In contrast, the maximum precipitation values at the four stations range from 2420.2 mm (Do Luong station) to 2430.1 mm (Nam Dan station), indicating that the wettest period occurred in the east and northeast of the study area, with a maximum value of 2420.2 mm.

Table 2. Precipitation statistical features at observation stations during the period 1998-2020

No.	Station	Minimum (mm)	Maximum (mm)	Mean (mm)	SD (mm)	CV (%)
1	Yen Thuong	1100.7	2356.3	1861.3	336.5	0.19
2	Dua	1309.7	2312.9	1755.5	324.1	0.20
3	Do Luong	1149.5	2420.2	1852.2	324.5	0.21
4	Nam Dan	1086.1	2430.1	1846.8	369.4	0.22

The mean precipitation values at the four stations range from 1755.5 mm to 1861.3 mm, indicating that Yen Thuong station experienced the highest average precipitation, while Dua station experienced the lowest average precipitation. The standard deviation (SD) of precipitation values at the four stations ranges from 324.1 mm to 369.4 mm, indicating that Nam Dan station had the highest variability in precipitation, while Dua station had the lowest variability. The coefficient of variation (CV) of precipitation values at the four stations range from 0.19 to 0.22, indicating that Yen Thuong station had the lowest variation in precipitation, while Nam Dan station had the highest variation. This suggests that Yen Thuong station experienced a more consistent precipitation pattern, while Nam Dan station experienced a more variable precipitation pattern. Overall, the analysis of the precipitation characteristics at the four stations provides valuable insights into the local climate patterns and precipitation trends.

3.3 Temporal change trends detection

The analyzed results of temporal change trends of precipitation at 04 observation stations across Nghe An province during the period 1998 - 2022 are given in Table 3. To temporal change trends detection at of precipitation at 04 observation stations, a significance level of 95% was used for both Man-Kendall test and Sen's slope estimator. Analysis results revealed that the Kendall's tau value is 0.304, 0.333, 0.239 and 0.268 at Yen Thuong, Dua, Do Luong and Nam Dan stations, which indicates a moderate trend towards increasing precipitation (Figure 4a). The p-critical value is 0.039 and 0.023 at Yen Thuong and Dua stations, which is less than the significance level of 0.05, indicating that the trend is not statistically significant. While at Do Luong and Nam Dan stations, the p-critical values are 0.108 and 0.070, which is greater than the significance level of 0.05, indicating that the trend is statistically significant. For the Sen's slope, results showed the values are 21.91, 26.88, 16.01 and 21.36, which represents the increasing trend and statistically significant of precipitation across the study area over time (Figure 4b).

Table 3: Results of the trend detection based on the Man-Kendall and Sen’s slope estimator at precipitation observation stations across the study area

No.	Station	Kendall's tau	p-critical	Sen's slope
1	Yen Thuong	0.304	0.039	21.91
2	Dua	0.333	0.023	26.88
3	Do Luong	0.239	0.108	16.01
4	Nam Dan	0.268	0.070	21.36

Overall, the analysis of the trend detection results indicates that all four stations exhibit a trend towards increasing precipitation, with Dua station experiencing the strongest trend. The results also suggest that the rate of change in precipitation varies across the stations, with Yen Thuong and Nam Dan stations experiencing a moderate rate of change, while Do Luong station experiences a weak rate of change (Figure 5).

Figure 4: Precipitation variation trends based on the Mann-Kendall test and Sen’s slope estimator

These findings have important implications for water resource management and agricultural planning in the region. The increasing trend in precipitation at all four stations suggests that the region may experience more frequent and severe flooding events in the future, which could have significant impacts on agricultural and forestry activities. Therefore, it is essential to develop strategies to mitigate the effects of flooding and to ensure that water resources are managed sustainably in the region.

Figure 5: Temporal trend of precipitation based on the Mann-Kendall test across the study area during the period 1998 – 2022

4. Conclusions

The investigated the precipitation variation trends across Nghe An Province of Viet Nam under the background of climate variability based on the collected precipitation data series during the period of 1998-2020. The results of the trend detection based on the Mann-Kendall test and Sen's slope estimator indicated that all four stations exhibit a trend towards increasing precipitation, with Dua station experiencing the strongest trend.

The increasing trend in precipitation at all four stations suggests that the region may experience more frequent and severe flooding events in the future, which could have significant impacts on agricultural and forestry activities. Therefore, it is essential to develop strategies to mitigate the effects of flooding and to ensure that water resources are managed sustainably in the region.

Overall, this study contributes to the understanding of precipitation variation trends in Nghe An Province of Viet Nam under the background of climate variability, and provides valuable insights for water resource management and agricultural planning in the region.

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